

Hyperlinks, Internet, Number and Set Theory

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Abstract:

We rely on Internet as per hyperlinks, and in this paper, we shall attempt to study about Hyperlinks, along with discussion of Artificial Intelligence.

Keywords: Hyperlinks, Internet, Numbers, Set Theory, Internet

Introduction:

Hyperlinks serves as address to allow us to visit any page. Link in general meaning, too does means linking means, and without wasting our time, we shall proceed to study with few examples.

Author's OID is 1.3.6.1.4.1.37476.9000.130, provided by Viathinksoft, one of Registered Authorities to provide Object Identifier.

That means, those numbers would serve to identify author(me), along with my institution.

Author has PEN Id, provided by IANA, and is 57490, which too would serve as an identifier.

Each of varying identifiers works in similiar purposes, which is like as tracing address, or identifying, relying on database, that we do submit.

Author has similiarly registered in NTP id, Twiki name, ISNI number, Ringold Id, Wikidata Id, and various other places.

That was description about author. Now, let us observe, how can we work, with Artificial Intelligences, with our written computing codes, as author doesn't possess sound knowledge in computing, but thought, working process of internet and hyperlinks would be similiar.

Now let us begin with an URL

https://vixra.org/author/arjun_dahal, which has few short essays, and let us take again, particular URL from that page as <https://vixra.org/abs/2106.0018>

In those two URLs, one has collected information, and another has specific, where too numerical methods have been assigned, for identification of papers.

Now look at another URL from Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/record/4899856#.YLszWhjBVPz>

We shall begin with discussion of submissions of manuscripts for publication.

Question:

How would both of those URL would perform work, as well as administrations, if I would update my paper, in either of them?

If I would update in Zenodo, then updated link in Vixra, might provide us updated link, or even Datacite, and DOI foundation might provide us with link, to updated file, relying on updated version.

How would then OID, PEN ID, and other identifiers would find the materials, of authors, to provide individual archival record, as per listing.

Examples can be talked about ORCID registry, and other such platforms, but still question is posed by convininency, how would any fellow, can have a unique identifier to find all of his works in Internet.

Use of Keywords to search would just reduce, our work, by reducing work that we do write in abstract, in terms of only one or few words, and our programming tools too might search on any database, based on certain values and parameters.

Outcomes:

When such numbers are assigned, based on identifications, then we might hope, to define some values, where, based on values, our entire work in internet, would be represented by just one link, or hyperlink.

Common examples would be like as creating webpages, then linking sources, or having blogs to create of our works in Internet, and that would be again discussion of topics about links, hyperlinks, URL and webpages, and It would again be question, how to study numbers, then make set of numbers to define

some values. That would allow us to form set and subsets, of any directory, and we irrespective of numbers

Acknowledgements:

All administrations which does registration, as per their working structure.

References:

1. In-Text References
2. Websites of various pages, which I don't know when I accessed last, but do think, even webpage designers and programmers do keep archival records.